

The role of hybrid of tamarind and guar gum in the removal of unwanted metals from waste water

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Abstract : The present work is used for the treatment of effluent streams containing Ni^{II}, Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} by hybrid of tamarind and guar gum. Tamarind and guar gum were activated by heat treatment and with concentrated sulphuric acid. The optimum shaking speed, mass of adsorbent, contact time, pH, temperature were determined. The paper also discusses the effect of ratio of tamarind and guar gum as an adsorbent for removal of various heavy metals. The article presents a brief review on the mechanism of heavy metal adsorption by hybrid of tamarind and guar gum. The maximum removal efficiencies were 85% for Ni^{II} at pH 7, 80% for Cd^{II} at pH 5 and 88% for Pb^{II} at pH 5. This article also shows that hybrid is comparatively better than lonely tamarind and guar gum.

Keywords : Adsorption, hybrid, waste water, heavy metals.

Introduction

Most of the industries generally discharge untreated effluents into the neighboring fields or drains. These effluents not only contain nutrient that may stimulate growth of many crops but also have toxic chemicals, which may retard germination. The major sources of water pollution are domestic wastes and industrial wastes, which are discharged into natural water bodies. In India about 80% of water supply of a city finds its way back into the drainage system as domestic and industrial waste. These are discharged into the water bodies without being treated properly. According to NEERI, about 75% of India's inland water is unfit for human consumption. The major cause of deterioration of water quality in our country is the discharge of industrial waste water.

The demand for water is gradually increasing with growing population as well as rapid urbanization and industrialization in different parts of the world. Therefore, the removal of excess heavy metal ions from waste water is essential to protect human and environmental health¹. Many methods have been used to remove heavy metals from waste water are described in literature, including electrochemical precipitation^{2,3}, chemical precipitation⁴, membrane filtration⁵, and ion exchange treatment⁶, but these methods are expensive and not applicable in local

conditions. Therefore, it is necessary to develop easily available inexpensive and equally effective alternatives for waste water treatment. In India tamarind and guar gum are abundantly found in dry zones and are easily available. Adsorption is proved to be a cost effective and ecofriendly method for the removal of heavy metals. The uptake of metals by adsorbents has been attributed to the biochemical constituents namely, proteins, carbohydrates, and lignin that contain many functional groups including carboxyl, hydroxyl, amine moieties which are responsible for metal sorption. In recent years, several studies have been reported on various low cost adsorbents such as wool⁷, sawdust^{8,9}, wheat straw¹⁰, distillery sludge¹¹, activated neem leaves¹², activated tamarind seeds¹³, rice husk¹⁴, sphagnum moss peat¹⁵ etc. However many of these natural adsorbents low adsorbing capacity and most of them have are not locally available.

The present work describes the role of hybrid of tamarind and guar gum in the removal of metals like Ni^{II}, Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} from waste water.

Material and methods :

Adsorbents and reagents : The adsorbents tamarind and guar gum were obtained from the Ases Chemical Works in India's Jodhpur city.

All the chemical compounds used to prepare the reagent solution were of analytical grade (E. Merck Ltd., Bombay, India). The stock solution (1000 mg L^{-1}) of Ni^{II} , Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} was prepared by dissolving 2.207 g NiCl_2 , 1.630 g CdCl_2 and 1.155 g PbS salts in twice-distilled water. Concentration of metal solution ranged from 1.0 to 100.0 mg L^{-1} by dilution.

Instruments : A magnetic stirrer was used for the batch adsorption experiments. The metal solutions were filtered through Whatmann filter paper no. 42. The filtrates were then analyzed using atomic absorption spectrophotometer. The pH measurements were performed using pH meter.

General procedure : We studied the effects of ratio of tamarind and guar gum as an adsorbent, shaking speed, adsorbent mass, contact time, pH, temperature and initial metal ion concentration on adsorption of each metal using the experimental conditions shown in Table 1.

Eq. (1) is used to determine the percentage adsorption of the metal by adsorbent.

$$\% \text{ Adsorption} = \frac{C_0 - C_e}{C_0} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

where C_0 is initial metal concentration, C_e is metal concentration after shaking.

Characterization of adsorbent : Adsorbents are characterized by using FT-IR spectroscopy. IR spectra of treated tamarind (when alone), treated guar gum (when alone), and hybrid of tamarind and guar gum (60 : 40 and 70 : 30 of tamarind and guar gum) were taken. In IR spectra of tamarind (alone) (Fig. 1) various peaks were observed at 1170, 1310, 1480, 1605, 1700, 2037, 2600–3400 cm^{-1} due to -ONO, NO_2 , -C=C-, -C=N-, -C≡C- and hydrogen bonded -CHO, - NH_2 , -OH groups respectively. Also in case of guar gum (alone) (Fig. 2) various peaks were observed at 1400, 1640, 2930, 3100–3500 cm^{-1} due to - NO_2 , -C=C- and hydrogen bonded -CHO, - NH_2 , -OH groups respectively.

In IR spectra of hybrid of tamarind and guar gum (60 : 40) (Fig. 3) sharp peaks were observed at 1049, 1440, 1600, 1710, 2910 and 3410 cm^{-1} due to -ONO and NO_2 , -C=C-, -C=O, -C-H and -O-H stretching. In case of 70 : 30 ratio of tamarind and guar gum peaks were observed at 1049, 1404, 1610, 2932 and 3425 cm^{-1} due to -ONO, -C-O-C-, -C=C-, -C-H and -O-H stretching as shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 1. IR spectra of activated tamarind (when alone).

Fig. 2. IR spectra of activated guar gum (when alone).

Fig. 3. IR spectra of hybrid of tamarind and guar gum (60 : 40).

From IR spectra, we can conclude that in case of hybrid, functional groups are free and less hydrogen bonded. So these hybrids are of better efficiency as compared to tamarind or guar gum (alone).

Adsorption mechanism :

Based on the nature of heavy metal ions and adsorbent materials, it can be speculated that ion exchange or hydrogen bonding may be the principal mechanism for

Fig. 4. IR spectra of hybrid of tamarind and guar gum (70 : 30).

the removal of heavy metal ions. It has long been recognized that the heavy metal cations readily form complexes with O-, N-, S- or P- containing functional group in adsorbent. Adsorption process quite dependent on pH of the aqueous solution. In most cases, the % of adsorption of metal ions increased with an increase in pH up to a certain value and decreased with further increase of pH. Due to different properties of various heavy metal ions, the maximum adsorption takes place in a slightly different pH range for different metals.

In a specific pH range, for one specific heavy metal there may be a number of species present in solution, such as M^{2+} , MOH^+ , $M(OH)_2$, etc. At lower pH, the positive charged metal ion species adsorbed at the surface of the adsorbent by ion exchange mechanism. With increasing pH, metal ion species mainly neutral, may be adsorbed by hydrogen bonding mechanism. These mechanisms are shown in the following equation :

Ion exchange :

Hydrogen bonding :

Results and discussion

Effect of ratio of tamarind and guar gum :

The effect of ratio of tamarind and guar gum on removal efficiency was studied by taking all other parameters as constant according to Table 1.

From Fig. 5 it is clear that sorption is highly dependent on ratio of tamarind and guar gum. It also indicates that the hybrid is better than guar gum (when alone) and also better than tamarind (when alone). The maximum removal efficiency was obtained 85% at 60 : 40 (Tamarind : Guar gum) for Ni^{II} , 90% at 70 : 30 (Tamarind :

Fig. 5. Effect of ratio of tamarind and guar gum on the metal removal efficiencies.

Guar gum) for Cd^{II} and 78% at 60 : 40 (Tamarind : Guar gum) for Pb^{II}.

Effect of shaking speed :

During the process of shaking, energy was consumed. The maximum removal efficiency was obtained 80, 84 and 88% for Ni^{II}, Cd^{II}, Pb^{II}, respectively when shaking speed was 250 rpm.

This is due to the fact that when we increase the shaking speed, the consumed energy is used in the bond formation between adsorbent and metal. After 250 rpm the additional energy is used to break newly formed bonds between metal ion and adsorbent surface.

Effect of adsorbent mass :

The effect of mass of adsorbent on the adsorption of Ni^{II}, Cd^{II}, Pb^{II}, is presented in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6. Effect of the mass of adsorbent on the metal removal efficiencies.

From this figure it is clear that adsorption increases continuously with increasing adsorbent mass to a maximum at 30 g L⁻¹ for Ni^{II}, 35 g L⁻¹, for Cd^{II}, and 50 g L⁻¹ for Pb^{II}. After this maximum, there is no effect of mass of adsorbent on removal efficiency due to equilibrium formation.

Effect of contact time :

With the increase the contact time, the adsorption rate initially increases rapidly, after achieving equilibrium value (6 h for Ni^{II}, 4 h for Cd^{II} and 3 h for Pb^{II}) the removal efficiency decreases by 2–10% with increasing contact time. This is probably due to the fact that after saturation, adsorption and desorption processes occur simultaneously.

Effect of pH :

There is a remarkable effect of pH on the removal efficiency of adsorbent. In a pH range 1–9, metal adsorp-

tion increases with increasing pH up to a certain value (pH 4 for Ni^{II}, 5 for Cd^{II}, and 5 for Pb^{II}) and then decreases with further pH increasing (Fig. 7). It has been already explained by mechanism.

Fig. 7. Effect of pH on the metal removal efficiencies.

Effect of temperature :

It is apparent that by increasing the temperature the adsorption efficiency increase till a maximum, after this maximum the adsorption process increases with further increasing temperature (Fig. 8).

Fig. 8. Effect of temperature on the metal removal efficiencies

It is readily understood that the number of available adsorption sites increases by increasing the temperature and it, therefore, results in the increase of removal efficiency. The decrease in adsorption efficiency after 315 K is due to the damage of active sites on high temperature.

Conclusion :

The role of hybrid technology using tamarind and guar gum in the removal of Ni, Cd, and Pb from aqueous solution has been investigated. The investigations are quite useful in developing an appropriate technology for effluent treatment.

The ion exchange and hydrogen bonding mechanism explain the heavy metal adsorption by adsorbent. The adsorption efficiency is influenced by ratio of tamarind and guar gum, shaking speed, adsorbent mass, contact time, pH, and temperature. Adsorption studies show that the hybrid is better as an adsorbent than single tamarind or single guar gum. The process is economically feasible and easy to carry out.

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References

1. R. K. Srivastava, V. Sehgal and A. Sen, A. P. H. Publishing Corporation, New Delhi, 2002.
2. D. M. Roundhill and H. F. Koch, *Chemical Society Reviews*, 2002, **31**, 60.
3. N. Meunier, P. Drougi, C. Montance, R. Hausler, G. Mercier and J. F. Blais, *J. Hazard. Mater.*, 2006, **137**, 581.
4. M. Uysal and A. Irfan, *J. Hazard. Mater.*, 2007, **149**, 482.
5. C. A. Kozłowski and W. Walkowiak, *Water Res.*, 2002, **36**, 4870.
6. E. Pehlivan and T. Altun, *J. Hazard. Mater.*, 2006, **B-134**, 149.
7. M. Dakiky, M. Khamis, A. Manassra and M. Mereb, *Adv. Environ. Res.*, 2002, **6**, 533.
8. L. J. Yu, S. S. Shukla, L. D. Kenneth, A. Shukla and J. L. Margrave, *J. Hazard. Mater.*, 2003, **B-100**, 53.
9. M. Ajmal, A. H. Khan, S. Ahmad and A. Ahmad, *Water Res.*, 1998, **32**, 3085.
10. C. Li, H. Chen and Z. Li, *Proc. Biochem.*, 2004, **39**, 541.
11. K. Selvaraj, S. Manonmani and S. Pattabhi, *Bioresour. Technol.*, 2003, **N89**, 207.
12. B. V. Babu and S. Gupta, *Adsorption*, 2008a, **14**, 85.
13. B. V. Babu and S. Gupta, *J. Environ. Eng. Sci.*, 2008b, **7**, 553.
14. T. G. Chuah, A. Jumasiah, I. Azni, S. Katayon and S. Y. Choong Thomas, *Desalination*, 2005, **175**, 305.
15. Y. S. Ho, D. A. J. Wase and C. F. Forster, *Water Res.*, 1995, **29**, 1327.
16. Y. S. Ho and G. McKay, *Trans. Ichem. E.*, 1999, **77(B)**, 165.
17. Y. S. Ho and G. McKay, *Water Res.*, 2000, **34**, 735.
18. S. Arya, R. P. Bisht, R. Tomar, O. P. Toky and P. J. C. Harris, *Druce in India, Agroforestry Systems*, 1995, **29**, 1.
19. H. A. Elliot and C. P. Huang, *Water Res.*, 1981, **15**, 849.
20. J. Wang, *Process Biochem.*, 2002, **37**, 847.
21. E. Erdem, N. Karapinar and R. Donat, *J. Colloid Interf. Sci.*, 2004, **280**, 309.
22. G. E. Marquez, M. J. P. Ribeiro, J. M. Ventura and J. A. Labrincha, *Ceram. Int.*, 2004, **30**, 111.
23. D. Mohan and K. P. Singh, *Water Res.*, 2002, **36**, 2304.
24. I. Gaballah and G. Kilbertus, *J. Geochem. Explor.*, 1998, **62**, 241.